

“Change has to come from more established scholars.”

Aileen Fyfe, Professor
of Modern History at the
University of St Andrews

Open access book publishing is on the rise but Fyfe says many academics still shy away from it. She fears many senior academics also advise early career scholars to take the well-trodden, prestige publishing route, thinking it is safer and will open more doors.

Fyfe thinks this is a shame and that senior academics need to agitate for change. She published her first open access book in 2022 in collaboration with three post-doctoral researchers and says it has been a hugely positive experience.

It wasn't a decision she took lightly. She too was concerned that it would affect the career prospects of her early career researchers, but the reality has been very different. The book has generated a lot of interest, with 1,800 downloads in the first month. One of Fyfe's researchers has since published their own book open access, and is working on another.

Fyfe says senior scholars need to get behind open access book publishing.

“We need to see senior members of the profession speaking out in favour, demonstrating that it can be done and that the publishing process is very similar in terms of editorial boards, peer review and copy editing.”

Fyfe's advice on how senior scholars can break down barriers

Share how open access increased their profile and visibility: Fyfe saw 1,800 downloads in one month

Show it can (and should) be done with rigorous and quality publishing standards

Share the benefits of born-digital publications, like flexibility of format and style

Challenge perceptions in their communities and organisations